

STUDY OF THE CONDITIONS OF PRECIPITATION OF CUPRIC HYDROXIDE FROM CUPRIC SALTS BY SOLUBLE HYDROXIDES. PART I. REACTION BETWEEN SOLUTIONS OF CUPRIC SULPHATE AND SODIUM HYDROXIDE

BY ARUN K. DEY AND SATYESHWAR GHOSH

Precipitation of cupric hydroxide from a solution of cupric sulphate by the addition of sodium hydroxide has been studied. The colour of the precipitate is found to vary remarkably with the amounts of alkali added and also with time. The amount of sodium hydroxide needed for the complete precipitation of copper in solution is about 10% less than the equivalent quantity and this behaviour can be explained on the basis of hydrolytic adsorption of the SO_4^{2-} radical by cupric hydroxide when the medium is not sufficiently alkaline. It is further concluded that the adsorption of sulphate diminishes with the increase in the alkalinity of the medium, because of the amphoteric character of cupric hydroxide. This happens at lower temperatures, for example at 30° , but at 50° and 80° , the adsorption of sulphate becomes negligible and complete precipitation occurs practically with equivalent quantities.

The colour and properties of cupric hydroxide precipitated by alkali solutions vary according to the conditions of precipitation. The amount of alkali required for complete removal of copper from the solution of cupric sulphate is also smaller than the equivalent amount. This paper records some of the results on the nature of such hydrated cupric oxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

The concentration of the cupric sulphate (AnalaR) solution used was $0.4805M$ and that of sodium hydroxide, $1.9665M$. Cu was estimated both gravimetrically and volumetrically; sulphate was estimated as BaSO_4 .

From 10 c. c. of the cupric sulphate solution, the hydroxide was precipitated by different quantities of alkali and the colour of the precipitates obtained varied from light blue to green and finally with increasing amounts of alkali, and in general, showed a tendency to darken with time. It was further noted that copper was completely precipitated when 1.759 equiv. of alkali were added, but the filtrate remained neutral even with 1.821 equivs. of alkali, and with further increase of alkali, the filtrate too became alkaline.

Now, to 10 c. c. of the cupric sulphate solution, taken in graduated flasks, were added different volumes of alkali solution, measured from a microburette, and the total volumes raised to 100 c. c. The flasks were left overnight, and alkali was estimated in the supernatant liquids. The compositions of the precipitates were calculated on the basis, that the amount of alkali used up completely converted the cupric sulphate into the hydroxide. The excess of the cupric sulphate was considered to be associated with the hydrated oxide as adsorption complexes or basic salts. The precipitation was effected at 30° , and the alkali estimated.

Finally the flasks together with the contents were kept in the thermostats maintained at 50° and 80° successively, and the amounts of alkali unused were determined in each case. The results are recorded below.

TABLE I

Amount of cupric sulphate = 4.805 mg. moles in 100 c. c. of the mixture.

Alkali added (mg. <i>M</i>)	Temperature = 30°		Temperature = 60°		Temperature = 80°	
	Alkali used up (mg. <i>M</i>)	Composition of the precipitate.	Alkali used up (mg. <i>M</i>)	Composition of the precipitate.	Alkali used up (mg. <i>M</i>)	Composition of the precipitate
0.6325	0.6325	CuO, 0.002(OH)	0.6125	CuO, 0.003(OH)	0.6125	CuO, 0.003(OH)
0.6359	0.4400	59CuO, SO ₄	0.5859	50CuO, SO ₄	0.5859	50CuO, SO ₄
0.4392	0.4092	47CuO, SO ₄	0.4392	—	0.4392	—
0.2426	0.2246	24CuO, SO ₄	0.2426	—	0.2426	—
0.0459	0.0359	16CuO, SO ₄	0.0459	—	0.0459	—
0.0193	0.0153	12CuO, SO ₄	0.0193	—	0.0193	—
0.6526	0.6526	0.6CuO, SO ₄	0.6526	—	0.6526	—
0.4560	0.4560	73CuO, SO ₄	0.4560	—	0.4560	—

With lower amounts of alkali, some copper was found to remain unprecipitated as shown by the blue colour of the supernatant liquid.

In view of the wide variations in the nature and the compositions of the precipitates, they were kept in contact with a normal solution of ammonia; the cupric oxides obtained with smaller amounts of alkali readily dissolved in ammonia, whilst those obtained with excess of alkali did not dissolve at all.

In another set of experiments, the hydrated oxide was precipitated with different quantities of alkali solution, the total volume of the heterogeneous mixture was raised to 100 c. c. and the precipitate allowed to settle for 24 hours at 30°. The amount of sulphate in the supernatant liquid was estimated as barium sulphate. Thus the amount of sulphate adsorbed was known. The results are recorded below.

TABLE II

Temperature = 30°.

Cupric sulphate taken = 4.805 mg. *M* in 100 c. c. of the mixture.

Amount of alkali added.	Sulphate in the supernatant liquid.	Sulphate associated with the precipitate.
0.4392 mg. <i>M</i>	4.480 mg. <i>M</i>	0.325 mg. <i>M</i>
0.6493	4.120	0.685
0.7593	3.686	0.969
7.8660	3.762	1.053

It was thought necessary to estimate the amount of sulphate retained by the hydrated cupric oxide even after thorough washing. The precipitates obtained after addition of alkali were washed till the filtrates were free from sulphate, and dissolved in Merck's pure hydrochloric acid, sulphate precipitated as barium sulphate, and estimated. The results are given below.

TABLE III

Cupric sulphate taken = 4.805 mg. *M* in 100 c. c. of the mixture.
Temperature = 30°

Amount of alkali added	Sulphate associated with the precipitate.	Composition of the precipitate.
9.8325 mg. <i>M</i>	Nil	CuO
9.4392	0.1580 mg. <i>M</i>	31.4CuO.SO ₄
8.9493	0.4120	11.7CuO.SO ₄
8.2593	0.6630	7.25CuO.SO ₄
7.6660	0.8280	7.43CuO.SO ₄

Tables II and III show that the amount of sulphate associated with hydrated cupric oxide, can only be washed partly and an appreciable quantity of sulphate is retained even after thorough washing.

DISCUSSION

The results recorded in Table I show that 10 c. c. of a cupric sulphate solution containing 4.895 mg. atoms of copper in solution, which should require 9.610 mg. *M* of sodium hydroxide, could completely be precipitated by 9.610 mg. *M* of alkali at 30°. This can be explained, either from the view of precipitation of a basic salt of copper (*cf.* Pickering, *Chem. News*, 1883 47, 187; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1883, 43, 337; Mehrotra and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 33, 216; Britton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2799), or that of the adsorption of the sulphate ions from sodium sulphate (produced in the interaction) by the hydrated cupric oxide and the consequent production of OH' ions by hydrolytic adsorption, which precipitates the excess of copper left out in solution due to the addition of an insufficient quantity of alkali. In either case, however, the precipitate is likely to be contaminated by sulphate ions (Tables II and III). It is significant to observe that the amount of sulphate found associated with the precipitate is always greater than the difference in the amount of sodium hydroxide required for complete precipitation as cupric hydroxide and the amount that was actually added. Thus when sodium hydroxide added is less by 0.7601 mg. equiv. than the amount to complete the formation of cupric hydroxide, the amount of sulphate associated is found to be 1.37 mg. equivs. Moreover, from Table I the filtrate appears to remain sufficiently alkaline even when the precipitate has the composition of a basic salt, 12CuO, SO₄. We have seen that well washed cupric hydroxide, obtained by the interaction of equivalent amounts of cupric salt and caustic soda solutions, when shaken with a solution of sodium sulphate liberates a detectable quantity of alkali. Thus the preferential adsorption of sulphate ions by hydrated cupric oxide can well explain the formation of an alkaline filtrate, even when sodium hydroxide added for precipitation is in smaller amounts than the equivalent quantity required for complete precipitation. This, therefore, leaves no doubt that sufficient amount of sulphate ions is adsorbed by cupric hydroxide and the following table confirms this observation even after thorough washing.

TABLE IV

Amount of cupric sulphate = 4.805 mg. moles in 100 c. c.

Amount of alkali added.	Amount of sulphate associated (in mg. <i>M</i>)		
	Total.	Unwashable.	Washable.
9.4982 mg. <i>M</i> .	0.325	0.153	0.172
8.5493	0.685	0.412	0.273
8.4560	0.999	0.663	0.306
7.8060	1.053	0.023	0.430

Our observations at 50° and 80° that for practically equivalent amount of the alkali added, the alkali remaining free remarkably decreases shows diminished preferential adsorption of sulphate which produces alkali.

It is of interest to note that the amount of sulphate found associated with cupric hydroxide goes on decreasing either as more and more of alkali is added or the temperature of the heterogeneous mixture is raised.

Dhar and Mehrotra (*loc. cit.*) have reported that in the estimation of copper as cupric oxide, the results are more near theoretical values, when larger amounts of alkali are employed for precipitation. This result is explainable from our viewpoint, that the adsorption of sulphate ion becomes negligible when cupric hydroxide is precipitated by a slight excess of alkali. The adsorption of alkali in this case is very small in comparison to the adsorption of sulphate ions. Further, the behaviour of cupric oxide to form cuprates is not remarkable, with the consequence, that the adsorption of OH' ions in presence of excess of alkali is loose and therefore washable.

The dissolution of the precipitates in ammonia has been qualitatively noted, and the results clearly indicate that cupric hydroxide, obtained in the presence of excess of alkali, has no tendency to form cuprammines, showing remarkable change in the property of cupric hydroxide precipitated with different amounts of alkali. This observation can be explained on the hypothesis that cupric oxide has an amphoteric character (Kohlschütter and Tuscher, *Z anorg. Chem.*, 1920, 111, 193; Weiser "The Hydrous Oxides", New York, 1926, p. 143), and that the acidic or the alkaline property will be guided by the alkaline or the acidic nature of the medium. It is well known that precipitates of basic character preferentially adsorb anions, while those of acid character, the cations; hence in presence of neutral or alkaline medium, when copper hydroxide is obtained, it is but likely to conclude that the acid character of copper hydroxide becomes predominant which deprives it of its capacity to adsorb an anion like sulphate. Hence in the formation of a complex ammine, where cupric hydroxide is likely to form a co-ordination compound with ammonia, this tendency will be more pronounced when the precipitate has neither acidic nor alkaline properties. More work, however, is necessary to confirm the view developed above, and further experimental work in this direction is in progress in this laboratory.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD,
ALLAHABAD.

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